

**TAILORING INTERPHASE PROPERTIES FOR DAMAGE CONTAINMENT
IN GRAPHITE / ALUMINUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES**

T. Erturk, V. Gupta, A.S. Argon, and J.A. Cornie
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, MA 02139

ABSTRACT

Many metal matrix composites (MMCs) experience property degradation due to the presence of diffusion or chemical reaction products at the fiber/matrix interface. This can be rectified by coating the fibers with diffusion barrier coatings which also serve as mechanical fuses to isolate the impinging reaction zone cracks by interface delamination. Requirements on the interface strength and toughness for the arrest of impinging cracks at the coating/fiber interface are given. The problem of a crack terminating at right angles to or located along the interface in a bimaterial is considered, and special problems associated with the graphite/aluminum system are identified. The toughness of the interface between an amorphous SiC coating and pyrolytic graphite substrate was measured using the double cantilever beam technique, and G_{IC} was determined to be 60 J/m^2 . This is a high value for the formation of new surfaces, and indicates inelastic energy dissipation on the sides of the crack, and can not be connected directly to the interfaces in graphite/aluminum composites. The role of interface strength and heterogeneity of fiber distribution in controlling the transverse properties are clarified, and the importance of wettability of fibers by the liquid metal in the solidification processing of MMCs is demonstrated.

NOMENCLATURE

$\sigma_{\theta\theta}$	Circumferential stress	σ_i^*	Interface cohesive strength
σ_{rr}	Radial stress	σ_j^*	Interface shear strength
$\sigma_{r\theta}$	Radial shear stress	σ_f^*	Fiber strength
σ_{rrI}	Interface radial stress	G_1	Shear modulus of coating
$\sigma_{xx\infty}$	Applied stress in close packed direction	G_2	Fiber shear modulus
		ν_1	Poisson's ratio of coating
$\sigma_{yy\infty}$	Applied stress in mid-close packed direction	ν_2	Poisson's ratio of fiber
		$\sigma_{yy}^1(90)$	Coating stress along interface
σ_e	Equivalent stress	$\sigma_{yy}^2(90)$	Fiber stress along interface
$\bar{\epsilon}$	Equivalent strain	$\sigma_{xx}(90)$	Interface normal stress
X_i	Interface fracture energy	$\tau_{xy}(90)$	Interface shear stress
X_f	Fiber fracture energy	$\sigma_{xx}(0)$	Crack tip stress (x-direction)
G_C	Strain energy release rate	$\sigma_{yy}(0)$	Crack tip stress (y-direction)
E	Young's modulus	$\sigma_{T\infty}$	Transverse tensile strength

INTRODUCTION

Traction transmitting interfaces in fiber reinforced composites are of primary importance in the proper transfer of the load from the matrix to the fibers and load sharing among the fibers. Although the level of interphase traction transmission governs both deformation and fracture behavior in these materials, our concern here will be the containment of damage (fracture) due to fiber/matrix reactions or cracks impinging on the fibers during longitudinal loading. Particular attention will be directed to the graphite fiber/aluminum matrix system in the form of unidirectional laminae. Additionally, we shall attempt to clarify the role of interfaces in the transverse tensile strength and fracture behavior in this system.

Most metal matrix composites are basically non-equilibrium systems, and in order to perform their intended application, they have to survive a high temperature processing operation, chemical interaction with the environment during processing or during service, and sustain residual stresses associated with cooling from the consolidation process. The chemical affinity of some fiber/matrix pairs, however, limit their high temperature capability. Although the formation of a few Angstroms thick diffusion or chemical reaction layer, driven by chemical potential differences, may be desirable for the formation of a chemical bond, the development of reaction zones, due either to processing or high temperature service, strongly degrades the strength of the fibers, and thus the composite itself [1]. Although the chemical interaction at the interfaces may vary from the formation of recrystallized zones [2] to preferential grain boundary attack [3]; from the formation of solid solutions to more complicated reaction products with positive volume misfit [4], the chief reason for the strength degradation of the fibers is the formation of microcracks. The resulting premature and often collective failure of the fibers during elastic loading or after plasticity develops in the matrix, may be triggered by the fracture of a single fiber due to the narrow distribution of the fiber strengths. Then, no fiber pull-out is exhibited (planar fracture surfaces), and the energy absorbing capability of the material during fracture is adversely affected.

An important advance towards rectification of the problems of interphase reactions and accompanying property degradation has been the introduction of diffusion barrier coatings which reduce the growth of reactions between the fiber and the matrix. We believe the central problem of metal matrix composites is to control (tailor) the strength and toughness of the interfaces between the fibers and the sacrificial coatings, and through proper choice of elastic properties prevent, by interface separation, the penetration of the cracks from the partially reacted outer layers into the fibers. Thus, in addition to being diffusion barriers, allowed to be partially consumed by the reaction with the matrix, coatings should act as mechanical fuses to arrest the impinging cracks, and contain the damage.

In addition to serving as diffusion barriers and mechanical fuses, there can be other demands on the coatings. Although techniques utilizing lower fabrication temperatures, such as powder metallurgy and other solid state consolidation methods reduce the extent of interphase reaction, it is the liquid infiltration techniques that provide an economical and near net shape production capability [5]. The chief reason for this is the low viscosity of the molten metal at relatively low superheats. In the case of solidification processing of metal matrix composites, the wettability of the fibers by the liquid metal, enhanced by the proper choice of coatings, is of primary importance in preventing fiber clusters or touching fibers. We will clarify the importance of fiber distribution defects in controlling the transverse properties later.

It is also conceivable that coatings could provide heterogeneous nucleation sites during the solidification of the matrix, as the solidification structure of the liquid infiltrated matrix depends critically on the nucleation kinetics. For example, the structure of the immediate vicinity of the fibers in eutectic forming aluminum alloy

matrixes [6] could be altered from an often brittle eutectic phase to a ductile α -aluminum phase by controlling the nucleation sequence. However, since there is no study of coatings as heterogeneous nucleation catalysts known to us, we shall not pursue this further here.

CENTRAL PROBLEM OF MMC'S: CRACK ARREST AT INTERFACES

As mentioned earlier, the main concern of this study is the protection of the fibers from interphase reaction induced damage. The key to the development of MMCs with superior strength and toughness lies in the design and control of the cohesive strength and toughness properties of the interface between the fiber and the sacrificial coating, as well as the elastic constants of the latter. Generally, the requirements on the interfacial strength are conflicting; for transverse strength of the composite adequate interface strength is needed, and for crack arrest by interface delamination in longitudinal loading, the strength of the interface should be low. Here, we shall assign upper bounds for the strength and toughness of the interface between the fiber and the barrier coating, and point out some areas for further research for the graphite/aluminum system. We shall then give experimental results on the measurement of work of fracture of this interface, using double cantilever beam experiments on simulated interphases. In a later section, we shall identify a lower bound for the interfacial strength to provide good transverse properties in this system.

The high strength and stiffness of the fibers are best exploited in longitudinal loading. The state of stress at the interfacial regions will deviate from uniaxial tension, and the mechanical interaction between the fiber and the matrix will also be affected by differences in the Poisson's ratio of the components. As the Poisson's ratio difference increases, for example with the onset of plastic flow in the matrix [7], the intensity of transverse stresses at the interface will increase. Nevertheless, because of the larger length over which the load can be transferred to the fiber, the interfacial stresses in longitudinal loading are less severe in comparison to transverse loading. Thus, as long as the fibers remain intact, the longitudinal strength of the composite should be relatively insensitive to interfacial bond strength, provided that the strength is adequate to transfer the load to the fibers.

The central problem of a reinforcing fiber coated with a brittle sacrificial layer in a ductile matrix (in our case Pitch 55 graphite fiber, coated with submicron thick amorphous SiC layers in an aluminum matrix) is depicted in Figure 1. There, a crack is shown nucleated in the reaction zone between the matrix and the coating, and impinging on the fiber/matrix interface. The circumferential stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ at $\theta=0$ probes the strength of the fiber, while the same stress at $\theta=\pi/2$ is responsible for interface separation. The radial shear stress $\sigma_{r\theta}$ at the interface ($\theta=\pi/2$), on the other hand, probes the shear strength of the interface. Thus, two failure processes are possible upon interaction between impinging cracks and interfaces: i) fiber fractures, or ii) fiber decouples from the coating in shear or in tension.

Strength Requirements to Protect Fibers

Interfacial strength requirements for the protection of fibers by crack arrest at the coating/fiber interface are given in Table 1. When the ratio of interface cohesive strength to fiber strength is less than the ratio of evolving elastic crack tip stresses responsible for interface separation and fiber fracture (i.e., the ratio of $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ at $\theta=\pi/2$ to $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ at $\theta=0$), interface will separate in tension, provided that the interfacial stresses are tensile. This condition leads to an upper bound for the interface cohesive strength. Likewise, when the ratio of interface shear strength to fiber strength is less than the ratio of $\sigma_{r\theta}$ at the interface ($\theta=\pi/2$) to $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ at $\theta=0$, the interface will separate in shear.

Figure 1. Central problem of metal matrix composites. Interfaces act as mechanical fuses to arrest impinging cracks by interface delamination.

TABLE 1
Strength and Toughness Requirements for the Protection of Fibers

$\frac{\sigma_{\theta\theta}(\pi/2)}{\sigma_{\theta\theta}(0)}$	$>$	$\frac{\sigma_i^*}{\sigma_f^*}$,	$\frac{\sigma_{r\theta}(\pi/2)}{\sigma_{r\theta}(0)}$	$>$	$\frac{\tau_i^*}{\tau_f^*}$,	$X_{i1} < \beta(G_1, G_2)X_{f1}$
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This bounds the maximum interface shear strength. When the ratio of interface cohesive strength to interface shear strength is less than the ratio $\sigma_{\theta\theta}/\sigma_{r\theta}$ at the interface, tensile separation will be preferred. Also, the toughness of the interface should be less than the toughness of the fiber or the coating for the crack to advance there.

Bimaterial Crack Tip Stresses

Many investigators including Zak and Williams [8], Erdogan [9], Swenson and Rau [10] and others [11] have analyzed the elastic stresses at the tip of a crack impinging at right angles to a bonded bimaterial interface having isotropic components. Of these, the approach used by Swenson and Rau [10] is the most direct and best documented. They showed that as the shear modulus of the cracked phase increased with respect to the uncracked component, the strength of the crack tip singularity increased. Their results depicting the effect of shear modulus ratio (components having equal Poisson's ratio of 0.3) on the relative magnitude of crack tip stresses in plane strain is reproduced in Figure 2. As can be seen, the crack tip stresses are very sensitive to the modulus ratio. In particular, the tensile stress parallel to the interface in the cracked component $\sigma_{yy}^1(90)$ increases rapidly as the cracked phase becomes stiffer. This may cause multiple horizontal fracture (crazing) in this phase. The tensile stress perpendicular to the interface, $\sigma_{xx}(90)$ which tends to split the interface, decreases rapidly and becomes slightly compressive as the cracked phase becomes relatively stiffer. On the other hand, the interface shear stress $\tau_{xy}(90)$ increases considerably as the modulus of the cracked phase increases. Thus, shear failure of the interface is most likely with stiffer coatings.

Figure 2. Effect of coating and fiber shear modulus ratio on the relative magnitudes of crack tip and interface stresses (from Swenson and Rau [10]).

When the cracked material is the softer material, little vertical tensile stress develops in it. The tensile stress in the vertical direction in the uncracked phase is slightly larger than crack tip vertical tensile stress. As the cracked component becomes softer, the tensile stress probing the cohesive strength of the interface $\sigma_{xx}(90)$ increases while interfacial shear stress $\tau_{xy}(90)$ decreases. Thus, with softer coatings, the most likely failure mode is the interface tensile splitting. Swenson and Rau's solution also indicates a significant effect of the Poisson's ratio of the component phases on the crack tip stresses.

Special Problems of Interfaces in Graphite/Aluminum Composites

Using Swenson and Rau's solution, upper bounds to the interface strength can be obtained for isotropic fibers and coatings, exhibiting no inelastic deformation. However, the analysis of Swenson and Rau and various other authors is not applicable to graphite/aluminum composites because of the extreme anisotropy of the graphite fiber; the longitudinal Young's modulus of the Pitch 55 graphite fiber is 380 GPa, whereas the radial modulus is 14 GPa. In addition, graphite fiber may undergo plastic shear because of the weak bonding between the basal planes. In the next section, we shall show evidence that pyrolytic graphite undergoes plastic deformation under similar situations. Ting and Hoang [12] and Arin [13] analyzed the singularities at the tip of a crack terminating perpendicular to the interface between two anisotropic materials using numerical techniques. Since results can not be extracted for the general case from numerical solutions, a separate stress analysis for the bimaterial crack tip problem for the graphite/aluminum system is necessary to establish upper bounds for the interface strength.

Crack Along the Interface

After decoupling the fiber from the coating, we need to determine the stresses at the tip of the crack which now lies along the interface. This is important because if

the stresses generated at the tip of the vertical crack exceed the fiber strength, fibers will break, and if this occurs at a relatively small distance from the main crack the aim of crack arrest at the interfaces will be defeated. Also, stresses at the tip of the vertical crack may cause plastic deformation in the fiber as the crack advances along the interface. In this case, the energy consumed during the advance of the crack along the interface will include the energy required to deform the fiber in addition to the work of fracture of the interface. The problem of a crack along the interface between two isotropic materials was studied by many investigators [14,15], where elasticity theory solutions involve oscillatory stress singularities [16,17]. In view of the complexities encountered with two isotropic media, the interfacial problem of a bimaterial consisting of an isotropic elastic and an anisotropic plastic component is even more complicated. It is clear, however, that a better understanding of the mechanics of the interfaces in graphite/aluminum composites is necessary to tailor the key interface between the fiber and its protective coating.

MEASUREMENT OF FRACTURE ENERGY OF INTERFACES

In the control of interface properties such as (tensile) cohesive strength, work of fracture, and the terminal shear strength, an important prerequisite is that these properties should be measurable, and the effectiveness of the crack arrest in composites should be demonstrable. Performing experiments on actual interfaces in a composite is difficult because of geometrical constraints. Performing experiments with 10 μm diameter fibers are likewise difficult. Thus, experiments utilizing simulated interfaces on a larger scale are desirable. This requires finding material surfaces having the same characteristics as that of the fiber, which can then be adopted for macroscopic testing.

The structure of the Pitch 55 fiber consists of corrugated lamellae of the basal planes which are axially aligned and meet the surface at right angles. Pyrolytic graphite (PG), with layered basal planes (albeit in nodular form) can be used to simulate the Pitch 55 fiber surfaces; the planar surfaces parallel to the c-axis is similar in structure to the fiber surfaces. The properties of PG and Pitch 55 fiber is given in Table 2. The low strength of the PG may be due to its spherulitic (nodular) morphology.

TABLE 2
Properties of Pitch 55 Graphite Fiber and Pyrolytic Graphite

	Pyrolytic Graphite	Pitch 55
E_{long} (GPa)	28.5	380
E_{trans} (GPa)	7	14
Density (g/cm^3)	2.2	2.0

Table 2 indicates that the parallel between the PG and the Pitch 55 fiber is not good when mechanical properties are concerned. This is surprising because both materials are of same chemistry having highly oriented basal planes. Thus, the transfer of experimental results from model planar interfaces to actual interfaces in the composite will require a complete understanding of the interfaces.

Measurement of interface properties is not a new problem in thin film and coating technology, and the literature is replete with practical techniques for the measurement of some average properties of thin film or coating interfaces, recently reviewed by Mittal [18]. Here, we shall point out to some critical views omitted by Mittal, and cover the salient developments following his review briefly.

The preferred test for the measurement of interfacial properties should measure the state of adhesion directly using simple fundamental laws of mechanics rather than using some complicated models which themselves are based on unverifiable assumptions. For example, in the scratch test [19], the process of scratch formation is complex and can not be explained in terms of simple mechanical models. Furthermore, there is no preferential failure at the film/substrate interface, and the size and shape of the stylus can influence the mode of failure. In the periodic cracking technique utilized by Chow, Liu and Penwell [20] and by Davutoglu and Aksay [21], the complex state of stress at the edge of the film in contact with the substrate is not taken into account. More detailed stress field modeling, such as carried out by Yang and Freund [22] using sliding stress intensity factors, are necessary. The indentation technique of Chiang, Marshall and Evans [23], requiring the presence of interface in the vicinity of plastic zone, is also based on a fairly complicated model, and does not measure the fracture toughness of the interface directly. On the other hand, the double cantilever beam test provides a direct method to measure the adhesive fracture energy, and has been used earlier for this purpose [24,25]. Here, for a valid test for the properties of the interface alone, the components should not deform plastically, the interface should preferably be less tough than the components, and stable testing conditions should be maintained during load drops initiated by the fracture of the interface.

Experiments

The surfaces, perpendicular to the basal planes, of rectangular specimens of PG, 150 mm long, 6.3 mm wide, and 3.2 mm thick, were coated with 0.3 μm thick amorphous SiC of near stoichiometric composition, using radio frequency plasma assisted chemical vapor deposition techniques. The substrate temperature was approximately 500C during the low energy ion bombardment. The coated specimens were annealed at 600C for 1/2 h for dehydrogenation, and two of the coated strips were bound together using a thin layer of tough permabond glue (ESP 109) over half of the length so as to create a crack of 75 mm. The bonded strips were annealed at 200C to cure the glue. The free ends of the graphite strips were connected to the Instron loading train by means of 200 μm diameter tungsten wires. The cantilevers were pulled apart at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. Stable testing conditions were obtained by maintaining the unloading stiffness of the specimen less than the stiffness of the testing machine [26].

Since the glue, the SiC coating, the PG substrate, and the glue/coating interface were tougher than the substrate/coating interface, fracture initiated and propagated there. A typical load versus load point displacement plot is given in Figure 3. In some tests the crack initiated (or terminated) in the glue layer; load increments due to such deviations were not considered. Scanning electron micrographs of the fractured interfaces, and the stereo-pairs of them, indicated that in a small portion of the fracture area (approximately 10%) the crack dipped into the glue layer, as shown in Figure 4, and the results were corrected for this. To this end, the fracture work of the glue was determined using two steel strips glued together in a double cantilever configuration. Likewise, the work of fracture of the PG was determined separately using the same technique.

The fracture separation work $2\chi_i = G_{IC}$ was determined to be $60 \pm 6.9 \text{ J/m}^2$ [26] for the coating/graphite interface, 125 J/m^2 for the glue, and 68 J/m^2 for the PG. The high value for the fracture energy for the interface indicates additional inelastic energy dissipation in the surroundings. Similarly, a work of fracture of 68 J/m^2 for the PG can not be attributed to the formation of new surfaces only. It is expected that PG, with a low interlaminar shear yield strength of 52 MPa, plastically deforms due to the crack tip induced shear stresses, see Figure 5. Likewise, considerable energy can be expended through the plastic deformation of the glue, which is further accentuated if the glue is porous. Experiments with varying glue thickness, to be

Figure 3. A typical load-displacement plot obtained during double cantilever beam G_{1c} testing. The rise at the end is due to crack advancing in the glue layer [26].

Figure 4. Scanning electron fractograph of a separated SiC/PG interface. Crack dipped a PG fracture surface from a double cantilever beam test indicating plastic shear [26].

extrapolated to zero glue thickness, could not be carried out due to difficulties associated with controlling the glue thickness precisely.

* TRANSVERSE PROPERTIES

Because of the complexity of the stress field at the interfaces, the transverse loading has been studied chiefly by numerical techniques. The normal (radial) stress developed at the interface is much larger than the shear stress. Hence, failure is more likely to occur by tensile debonding than by shear slippage. In a recent elastic-plastic finite element analysis of transverse tension behavior of graphite/aluminum composites, made up of ideal hexagonal periodic cells, Zywiec [27] considered loading in i) close packed (CPD), and ii) mid-close packed (M-CPD) directions, as shown in Figure 6.

Elastic and elastic-plastic stress concentration factors for the interfacial radial stress are presented in Table 3 for both x- and y-loading as a function of volume fraction [27].

Figure 6. Close packed, and mid-close packed directions in transverse loading.

TABLE 3
Transverse Stress Concentrations for Graphite / Pure Aluminum [27]

V_f	Elastic Stress Concentration			
	0.4	0.6	0.8	
$\sigma_{rrl}/\sigma_{xx\infty}$	0.44	0.56	0.74	$(\sigma_{xx\infty})$
$\sigma_{rrl}/\sigma_{yy\infty}$	0.60	0.82	1.04	$(\sigma_{yy\infty})$
	Elastic-Plastic ($\bar{\epsilon}=0.01$) Stress Concentration			
σ_{rrl}/σ_e	1.14	1.55	2.40	$(\sigma_{xx\infty})$
σ_{rrl}/σ_e	1.14	1.14	1.33	$(\sigma_{yy\infty})$

Table 3 indicates a stress deficiency in the fibers during elastic loading. As plasticity develops heterogeneously in the matrix and spreads throughout, the negative pressure increases due to Poisson contraction, leading to higher interfacial stresses. A stress concentration factor of 2.40 is obtained for a volume fraction of $V_f=0.80$ at the macroscopic strain of $\bar{\epsilon}=0.01$. Based on these factors, and assuming crack free interfaces, the lower bound on the interface strength σ_i^* is:

$$\sigma_i^* = k\sigma_{T\infty} \quad (1)$$

where k is the maximum stress concentration factor for a given fiber volume fraction, and $\sigma_{T\infty}$ is the desired transverse tensile strength of the composite.

In real composites, fiber distribution is rarely uniform, and in regions of near or touching fibers the local fiber volume fraction approaches the theoretical packing limit. Transverse failure will occur in regions of high local volume fraction due to high interfacial stresses developed in these regions. Thus, the k factor in Equation 1 will depend on the heterogeneity of fiber distribution, and the transverse properties will be improved significantly by developing processing techniques capable of producing uniform fiber spacings.

Experiments

Erturk, Cornie and Dixon [28] carried out stable transverse tension tests during load drops initiated by internal fractures in a graphite/6061 aluminum composite using small

gage length specimens tested in a stiff testing machine. They were able to stop the tests after approximately 15% load drop to observe the early development of fracture during transverse loading. These experiments were recently repeated using a similar graphite/2024 aluminum matrix composite, where failure also occurred in the elastic range, but developed in the interior of the tows, and again in fiber clusters or touching fibers (regions of high local volume fraction). Figure 7 shows one such cracked region

Figure 7. Development of transverse cracks **Figure 8.** Rather uniform distribution of at near or touching fibers inside tows in a electroless-Ni plated Pitch 55 graphite fi- Pitch 55 graphite/2024 aluminum composite. bers in a liquid infiltrated aluminum matrix.

in the graphite/2024 aluminum matrix system. These investigators [28] also found an effect of matrix alloying on the transverse strength of several graphite/aluminum composites. Since small distributions of Si, Cu and Mg should not change the wettability of the uncoated fibers significantly, similar heterogeneous distributions were observed qualitatively in all alloys. The transverse strength nearly doubled, from 22.7 MPa for the Al-Si alloy to 42 MPa for the Al-Mg alloy, indicating improved bond. However, these are still poor transverse strengths. It is clear that heterogeneity of distribution of fibers plays an important role as the interface strength in controlling the transverse properties.

WETTABILITY

A not so practical but instructive experiment will be described here. The surfaces of Pitch 55 graphite fibers were electroless-Ni plated using Bueler's Edgemet plating solution. Coated and uncoated bundles of ten fiber tows, 40 mm in length, were placed vertically in an evacuated quartz tube. A 2024 aluminum alloy rod was melted in vacuum above the fiber bundles. Following the submergence of the fibers by the molten metal, atmospheric pressure was released into the tube. The solidified specimens were sectioned and examined under a light microscope. The uncoated fibers were pushed together into a hexagonal array exhibiting no infiltration. The coated fibers, on the other hand, were dispersed uniformly as shown in Figure 8, surrounded, however, by intermetallic reaction products. This demonstrates the importance of the wetting properties of fiber coating surfaces in securing uniform fiber distributions, but also indicates the difficulty of obtaining uniform fiber spacings without side effects.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The central problem of metal matrix composites is to tailor the strength and toughness properties of the interface between the fiber and the coating, as well as the elastic properties of the latter to protect the fibers from impinging reaction zone cracks by crack arrest at interfaces by interface delamination. Since the available solutions do not involve anisotropy or plasticity, a detailed elastic-plastic bimaterial crack tip stress analysis for the SiC/graphite system is necessary to establish upper bounds for strength, toughness and elastic property requirements from the interphase regions.

The properties of the interface as well as the coating should be measurable directly using fundamental laws of mechanics, and the effectiveness of the tailored (engineered) interfaces in arresting impinging cracks should be demonstrable, for example, by enhanced fiber pull out in tension or fatigue. The coatings should serve as diffusion or reaction barriers, wetting agents, and heterogeneous nucleation catalysts, in addition to acting as mechanical fuses.

The double cantilever beam test provides a convenient direct method for the measurement of the fracture properties of interfaces. The toughness values obtained for both PG and the SiC/PG interface are approximately an order of magnitude higher than expected for surface formation only, and indicate inelastic energy dissipation in the sides of the crack. Although inelastic shear in the Pitch 55 fiber under the influence of impinging cracks is expected, our results on PG/SiC interface are not directly applicable for Pitch 55 fibers in an aluminum matrix, requiring further understanding of interface mechanics in this system.

Fiber distribution defects (clusters, touching fibers) play an equally important role as the interfacial strength in controlling the transverse properties. In the solidification processing of MMCs, improving the wettability of the fibers by the liquid metal significantly improves the fiber distribution, and should improve the transverse properties significantly.

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